

The Hot End of Political Parties

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According to the Second Law of thermodynamics the spontaneous evolution of human society is irreversible and exhibits a permanent increase of social temperature. Because the latter magnifies the effect of social entropy, it seems reasonable to expect the heat death of the partisan political system.

Political parties are associations of people with similar ideas and common interests, trying to accomplish their goals peacefully in practice. For the sake of transparency by simplicity let us consider a very idealized society, which consists only of two kinds of people, i.e. rights R and lefts L. These two components oppose each other and for this reason the social enthalpy of mixing $\Delta H = 2x(1 - x)$ is positive. Here x is the people fraction of rights, while the people fraction of lefts is naturally $1 - x$. Because the two social components above are distinguishable, there is obviously an entropy of mixing $\Delta S = -x \ln(x) - (1 - x) \ln(1 - x)$ as well, which is also positive because the people fractions are lower than 1. At constant social temperature T the characteristic potential of the system is Gibbs free energy $\Delta G = \Delta H - T\Delta S$. Introducing here the expressions above, one arrives at the well-known regular solution model [1] with

$$\Delta G(x, T) = 2x(1 - x) + T[x \ln(x) + (1 - x) \ln(1 - x)] \quad (1)$$

The x dependence from Eq. (1) possesses two minima and a maximum, where the derivative $\partial\Delta G/\partial x = 0$ vanishes. The maximum is naturally in the middle point $x = 50\%$, while the minima show the presence of two stable parties such as Republicans and Democrats in the USA. According to Eq. (1) their compositions obey the following relation $T = 2(1 - 2x)/\ln(1/x - 1)$, which is plotted in Figure 1. As is seen at low social temperature $T < 0.3$ the parties are almost pure, i.e. Republicans contains rights, while Democrats contains lefts. The increasing of the social temperature magnifies the effect of social entropy and, for instance, at $T = 0.8$ Republicans are 80% R and 20% L, while Democrats are vice versa. Note that the contemporary social temperature

in the USA is $T = 0.6$ [2]. By approaching the critical temperature $T = 1$ the two parties become indistinguishable with 50% R and 50% L, which leads to collapse of the political system. The reason is that the kinetic energy of any person is much higher than the attraction forces bringing people together. Above the critical temperature people become free individualists and nothing can force them to merge in stable parties. One can see similar processes nowadays in the European Union and particularly in Bulgarian politics.

Fig. 1 Two parties' composition at different social temperatures

Acknowledgments

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References

- [1] J.H. Hildebrand and R.L. Scott, *Regular Solutions*, Prentice-Hall, Englewood Cliffs, 1962
- [2] R. Tsekov, *Social Thermodynamics 2.0*, arXiv (2023) [2307.05984](https://arxiv.org/abs/2307.05984)